

Treatment-Prophylaxis of Milk Teeth Under the Influence of Hormonal Drugs Used during the Fetal Period

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Annotation: This article pays special attention to research aimed at improving the treatment of enamel hypoplasia in children, which occurs as a result of hormonal preparations in pregnancy. In this, measures are taken to determine the clinical-functional features of the specific course of diseases associated with diseases of the oral cavity in modern dentistry, which develop in children as a result of hormonal preparations in pregnancy.

Keywords: Enamel hypoplasia, physiotherapeutic measures, clinical-dental, laboratory, immunological and statistical methods.

At the global level, special attention is paid to research aimed at improving the treatment of enamel hypoplasia in children, which occurs as a result of hormonal preparations in pregnancy. In this, to determine the clinical-functional features of the specific course of diseases associated with diseases of the oral cavity in modern dentistry, which develop in children as a result of hormonal preparations in pregnancy; to assess the place of dental and physiotherapeutic measures in the complex treatment process; development of a comprehensive step-by-step approach plan that takes into account the somatic condition of children; offering therapeutic preventive methods based on violations of the functioning of the organs of the oral cavity in children caused by hormonal drugs in pregnancy; improvement of the development of methods for assessing the effectiveness of treatment is of particular importance.

Enamel hypoplasia, which occurs in their children as a result of taking hormonal drugs in pregnancy, occupies a special place in the prevalence, complexity in diagnosis and treatment. Scientific sources noted that "studies over the past twenty years have shown that pregnancy is caused by hormonal drugs, enamel hypoplasia in children is up to 42%, and these diseases, along with various syndromes, up to 30%". This situation is explained by the fact that the initial stages of diseases are accompanied by an absence of sufficient data on changes in both clinical and laboratory tests, as well as the absence of a single etiopathogenetic view among specialists. This indicates the need to improve the treatment and Prevention of the problem.

The production of thyrotropic (TTG) and adrenocorticotropic (ACTH) hormones is increasing during pregnancy. Thyroid stimulating hormone during pregnancy warns the thyroid gland and enhances the synthesis of thyroid hormones. Therefore, during pregnancy, some women may have increased thyroid levels and the number of people with thyroid problems may increase. Hyperfunctions of the thyroid gland can be caused by spontaneous abortions, and hypophysics leads to a violation of the formation of the brain in the child.

There are also obvious changes from the side of the adrenal glands. Most of the hormones of the cortical layer of the adrenals are produced in excess. It is worth noting that in the adrenal glands, a woman produces sex hormones, which, under the influence of a certain enzyme, are converted into hormones. During pregnancy, male sex hormones rise. During and outside pregnancy, this condition is called hyperandrogenism.

The easiest way to determine the level of the hormone hCG during pregnancy is with the help of available methods - this is done from home Tests (determination of high levels of chorionic

gonadotropin in urine). More informative is to determine the level of hormones in the blood in special laboratories. characterized by ughashi or its disappearance. Hormones are the chemical components of the holistic system of regulating body functions. These are substances of different natures capable of transmitting signals to cells. The result of these interactions is a change in the direction and intensity of metabolism, the growth and development of the body, the launch of important functions or their suppression and Correction.

Hormone is an organic chemical whose synthesis occurs in the glands of internal secretion or in the Endocrine regions of the glands of mixed secretion. They are released directly into the internal environment, spread through them and transferred to random target organs. Here they are able to have a biological effect, which is carried out through receptors. Therefore, each hormone has a special characteristic for a particular receptor. This means that these substances affect a function or process in the body. The classification of hormones by their effect, proximity to tissues and chemical structure makes this clear.

The modern classification of hormones considers these substances from many points of view. And they are united in one thing: only organic substances are called hormones, the synthesis of which occurs only in the body. Their presence is characteristic of almost all vertebrates, in which the regulation of body functions also represents the joint work of the humoral and nervous systems. In addition, in Phylogenesis, the humoral regulatory system predates the nervous system. This was the case even in primitive animals, although it was responsible for the most basic functions.

It is believed that the system of biologically active substances (BAS) and their specific receptors are even cell-specific. However, the concepts of " hormone "and" bass " are not the same. The hormone is called BAS, it is released in the internal environment of the body and affects a group of distant cells. So, in turn, acts on the local level. Examples of biologically active substances, also known as hormone-like substances, are callones. These substances are released by the cell population, they inhibit reproduction and regulate apoptosis. Examples of bass include prostaglandin. The modern classification of hormones determines a special group of eicosanoids for them. They are designed to locally regulate inflammation in tissues and carry out hemostasis processes at the level of arterioles.

Hormones from the chemical aspect ofbinos are divided into several groups. This also distinguishes them according to the mechanism of action, since these substances have different indicators of tropism for water and lipids. Thus, the chemical classification of hormones looks like this: • peptide group (excreted by the pituitary gland, hypothalamus, pancreas and parathyroid glands); • steroid group (excreted by the Endocrine part of the male gonads and the cortical areas of the adrenal glands); • group of amino acid derivatives (produced by thyroid and adrenal medulla); • group of eicosanoids (released by cells, synthesized from arachidonic acid).

It is noteworthy that female sex hormones also belong to the group of steroids. However, they are mostly not steroids: the effects of this type of hormone are not related to the anabolic effect. However, their metabolism does not lead to the formation of 17-ketosteroids. Although ovarian hormones are structurally similar to other steroids, this is not the case. Since they are synthesized from cholesterol, they are classified as other steroids to simplify basic chemical classifications. Hormonal substances can also be separated depending on the place of synthesis. Some form in peripheral tissues, others in the central nervous system. The way secretions and substances are released depends on this, which determines the peculiarities of the implementation of their effect. The classification of hormones by location looks like this:

hypothalamic hormones (release-factors);

- ✓ pituitary (tropical hormones, vasopressin and oxytocin);
- ✓ thyroid gland (calcitonin, tetraiadatironin and triiadatironin);
- ✓ parathyroid (parathyroid hormone;
- ✓ noadrenal (norepinephrine, epinephrine, aldosterone, cortisol, androgens;

- ✓ sexual (estrogens, androgens);
- ✓ pancreas (glucagon, insulin);
- ✓ tissue (leukotrienes, prostaglandins);
- ✓ Apud hormones (motilin, gastrin, etc).

The last group of hormonal substances is not fully understood. It is synthesized in the largest group of endocrine glands located in the upper intestines, liver and pancreas. Their purpose is to regulate the secretion of exocrine digestive glands and intestinal motility. Different hormonal substances have different effects on biological tissues. They are divided into the following groups:

- ✓ metabolic regulators (glucagon, triiodothyronine, tetraiodothyronine, cortisol, insulin);
- ✓ regulators of other endocrine gland functions (hypothalamic release factors, tropical hormones of the pituitary gland);
- ✓ regulators of calcium and phosphorus metabolism (parathyroid hormone, calcitonin and K altcitriol);
- ✓ water-salt balance regulators (vasopressin, aldosterone);
- ✓ regulators of reproductive function (sex hormones);
- ✓ stress hormones (norepinephrine, adrenaline, cortisol);
- ✓ regulating threshold and growth rates, cell division(somatotropin, insulin, tetraiodothyronine);
- ✓ regulators of the functions of the central nervous system, the limbic system (cortisol, adrenocorticotrophic hormone, testosterone).

The secretion of hormones occurs immediately after they are synthesized. They enter directly into the blood or tissue fluid. The last place of secretion is typical for eicosanoids: they should not move away from the cell, since they regulate the functions of the entire tissue population. And the hormones of the ovaries, pituitary gland, pancreas and others should be carried with blood throughout the body in search of target organs that have specific receptors for them. From the blood, they enter the intercellular fluid, where they are sent to the cell of the target organ. The above classification of hormones reflects the effect of substances on tissues and organs. Although this is only possible after binding to the chemical receptor. The latter are different and are located both on the cell surface and in the cytoplasm, on the nuclear membrane and inside the nucleus. Therefore, according to the method of signal transmission, substances are divided into two types:

- ✓ extracellular transmission mechanism;
- ✓ intracellular signaling.

This basic classification of hormones makes it possible to draw conclusions about the speed of signaling. For example, the extracellular mechanism is much faster than inside the cell. It is characteristic of adrenaline, norepinephrine and other peptide hormones. the intracellular mechanism is specific to lipophilic steroids. In addition, the benefits for the body are achieved faster with the synthesis of peptides. After all, the production of steroid hormones is much slower, and their signal transmission mechanism is also slowed down due to the need for protein synthesis and maturation. The extracellular mechanism is specific to peptide hormones that cannot enter the cytoplasm without a specific carrier protein outside the cytoplasmic membrane. This is not intended for him, and the signal itself is transmitted by changing the conformation of receptor complexes through the adenylylacyclase system. The intracellular mechanism is much simpler. It is carried out after a lipophilic substance enters the cell and meets cytoplasmic receptors. With it, it enters the nucleus and forms a complex of receptors, a hormone that acts on specific genes. Their activation leads to the onset of protein synthesis, the molecular effect of this hormone. The actual effect is already a protein that regulates the function given after synthesis and formation.

In this article, we will dwell on the topic of metabolism. In particular, attention is paid to accelerated, slow and standard type metabolism. We also study ways to slow down or speed up metabolism, define the general meaning of the term and dwell on concepts that are closely related to it. The human body is a very complex biological, chemical and physical mechanism. And his work largely depends on how it relates to the environment and how strong this connection is. In other words, the activity of all human organs depends on metabolism. To protect the human body from the harmful effects of pathogenic pathogens - viruses, the immune system has a mechanism that ensures the fight against infectious diseases. This is the production by cells, for example, T-lymphocytes, special substances, one of which is interferon gamma. The compound formed in the immune system plays the role of protecting cells.

Magnesium is an important chemical element that greatly affects the full functioning of the human body. Magnesium deficiency leads to serious health problems. But an excessive amount can harm the body. The article provides information on what deviations can occur against the background of a lack or excess of magnesium in the body, as well as the limits of the norm Thanks to Biotin, metabolic processes occur in the body. Taking biotin, a complex of vitamins based on it slows down the aging process, ensures the full functioning of the immune and nervous system and improves overall health If the child has a low calcium content, then the release of milk teeth is delayed. That is, it can come out from the age of 7-8 months, sometimes after the age of one year. This condition can manifest itself in the form of a sign of rickets disease.

If the calcium content is high, the teeth can come out more time-consuming and the ligaments end faster. That is, milk teeth can be born from the child's 3-4 months of age, sometimes even earlier, and in some cases, baby teeth. When a child is one year old, he should have 8 teeth in the norm in his mouth, and 20 teeth by the age of two. The following symptoms may occur when the child's tooth is exiting, but not necessarily (these signs are not always observed):

1. Baby's gums swell;
2. The baby's milk is painted in a white color;
3. A lot of saliva flows;
4. The child wants to take everything in his mouth and chew;
5. Body temperature increases (up to 37-38 degrees at most);
6. The child becomes more capricious;
7. A child's sleep is disturbed or sleep patterns change;
8. The child wants to bite the mother's chest or hand;
9. The child's appetite disappears;
10. The child's feces liquefy, go inside.

Do not confuse the above symptoms with the symptoms of certain diseases. For example, if the child's body temperature increases, the child coughs and his nose is leaking, then the child may have a cold. Or if the child's insides become stronger and vomiting is also added to him, then the child has an infectious disease, which must be treated immediately. Therefore, if you observe the above symptoms in the child and suspect that they are not a disease, then it is better to consult a doctor. When a child's tooth breaks, he will continue to bite everything. Because the teeth itch and there is a slight pain. That is why many whims do.

1. It is necessary to bring the child from special rubbers, which are sold in a pharmacy, helping to crack teeth. Recall that the rubber should be soft.
2. There are special gels that can help crack teeth:
3. Dentokind tablets are used to eliminate painful conditions at the exit of the teeth of lactating and young children, irritability, discomfort, ear pain, pain in the gums fever and diarrhea. 1 tablet to 3

times for children under 1 year old For children from 1 to 6 years old, 2 tablets are administered 3 times.

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